

USING AI IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN A PANDEMIC CONTEXT AND BEYOND

Culda L.

PhD.lecture

Aurel Vlaicu University Arad, Romania

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4230-5390>

Abstract

In a pandemic context, when we are used to classical methods, we have seen ourselves "thrown" into a virtual world, having to find teaching methods and teaching and assessment solutions, the pleasure of real interaction has been replaced by virtual communication which he often made mistakes. Thus, from the position of teacher in an engineering field, I had to find solutions for correct and attractive transitions of real information in the virtual environment.

Keywords: A.I; robotic education; virtual education; COVID pandemic.

In a pandemic context, we saw ourselves "thrown" into a virtual world, having to find innovative teaching methods.

The pleasure of real interaction has been replaced by virtual communication.

Thus, from the position of teacher in an engineering field, I had to find solutions for correct and attractive transitions of real information in the virtual environment.

Looking for solutions, I found an important help: artificial intelligence. Continuing studies in the field of artificial intelligence makes humanity question the importance of physical interaction in the didactic field.

Maybe human interaction will become even more important. The fact is that only teachers can truly understand the nuances of what goes on in the minds of their students in the classroom.

I believe that over time, we will discover that Artificial Intelligence becomes a valuable tool for trainers, but however powerful it may be, it cannot replace the human in the teaching field, because learning does not only refer to the exchange of information, but also to the emotional exchange that it helps to agree some subjects or to acquire some notions more easily.

The COVID pandemic has shown the enormous value of blended education: using artificial intelligence,

elearning tools and the magic of a teacher. Student interaction is much easier to facilitate in person and is generally very difficult to automate, making it a challenge for artificial intelligence.

I. HIGHER EDUCATION IN A PANDEMIC CONTEXT

The pandemic period has shaken the old teaching methods. We have found that there are times when we need to be physically separated and yet connected in order to grow as individuals and continue to produce added value.

We were brought up and taught with a classic, face-to-face education, where the teacher not only conveyed the information, but also made an educational correction by watching the gestures, positions, expression and interaction of the individuals. If in the economic area it is relatively easy to replace the human presence, in the didactic area, it is more difficult.

We were raised and taught with a classic, face-to-face education, in which the teacher not only transmitted the information but also made an educational correction by following the gestures, positions, expression and interaction of individuals. The pedagogy and methodology of teaching have changed over time, concluding that in addition to mainstream education, there is a need for education focused on individual abilities.

Fig.1. Schematization of the educational process in the web environment

In a pandemic context, when we are used to classical methods, we have seen ourselves "thrown" into a virtual world, having to find teaching methods and teaching and assessment solutions, the pleasure of real interaction has been replaced by virtual communication which he often was. making mistakes.

Thus, from the position of teacher in an engineering field, I had to find fast, correct and attractive solutions to transmit information in the virtual environment.

The construction of the engineer, made me describe what I want to offer and get during the information transfer period.

If we analyze the learning process from a systemic point of view, we will get a diagram.

Once the diagram was drawn, I proceeded to analyze each point to find viable solutions.

For the systemic analysis of the online teaching concept, we used petri nets.

Before preparing an engineering lesson that we have to give live on the Internet, we need to draw the didactic objectives that we have to achieve.

Fig.2. The descriptive Petri net of the distance learning process

Fig.3. Schematization of learning

1. What should I do?

In a context of a pandemic, when the interaction between individuals must be limited, the implementation of online or hybrid education was somewhat sudden, being fortuitous by the situation (in fields where it was not possible only online - such as engineering). Good! But I teach physically, how do I translate all the information online? What systems do they use? Thanks to those who were already creating online platforms, we had several means of communication that were free, accessible to everyone, easy to handle and to accommodate large groups of students: zoom, google classroom and Microsoft teams...etc. I chose the platform approved by the institution!

Another important aspect is the preparation of the teaching platform, by making a section of announcements, materials: course support, scientific articles, videos, etc., of questions and answers, so that the student can easily access the desired information.

2. How do I do the teaching?

Well, in a pandemic context, the accepted training system is online and refers to the set of technologies, means and procedures that work together to achieve the goal of training participants. Basically, e-learning represents the interaction between the teaching-learning process and Information and Communication Technology. When we talk about e-learning, we refer to a teaching-learning planned, organized and managed by an educational institution, which provides educational resources and directs learning in a logical way to be assimilated by students in their own way. Some of these methods can be used in addition to online learning to complement traditionally transmitted information so that the individual has access to better training. E-learning is not the best way to train, because human interaction cannot be replaced, but used properly, it is an optimal way to acquire new information.

Communication and collaboration teacher - student in e-learning can be done:

Synchronous: when all participants are connected at the same time to listen to a course or seminar by video conference. It is a good method of teaching and interacting with students, being able to raise problems and respond in real time. The teacher can observe the degree of understanding of a problem and can adjust his / her exposure in real time so that it is clearer.

Asynchronous: does not require attendance at a fixed date and time, but the student has the constraint of a deadline to solve a problem or topic. I had a very good feedback, when the student was able to manage the moment when he is working on a topic, (corrections and observations being made by e-mail) he can learn and do homework at his own pace.

This teaching / learning method has advantages and risks. Benefits include:

The dissemination of information quickly, results in an increase in the rate of knowledge acquisition and is beneficial for students, as they have quick access to sources of information: courses, seminars, web applications, animations, etc.

Independence of the student from space, the student can learn from where he wants saving time.

The student's time independence, the educational contents are covered at their own pace. He can listen to the course / seminar when it is scheduled but also at other times of the day, he having access to information outside of online classes.

Adaptive learning, in e-learning the teaching contents can be designed so that each student can go through the teaching materials at his own pace, and the tasks can be customized so as to address the learning needs of each.

Increase motivation through the use of multimedia elements and interactive learning. From the didactic experience I noticed that the new generations need concrete, the abstraction being more difficult for them. For the growing generations with technology in hand, the effect of using multimedia in learning is to streamline information retention and strengthen it. It is much easier for them to learn using simulations and animations than to deal with a problem in theory. For a teacher, this requires extra effort to adapt technical information and translate it into simulations and animations, but the result is worth it.

Stimulates independent thinking by carrying out stimulating projects.

The disadvantages of e-learning are:

Social differences prevent less financially gifted students from having access to computers / laptops, internet, additional systems needed for online schooling.

Student presence. Due to financial problems, many students work and not all of them can enter the scheduled time for online courses at work.

Lack of internet signal. Many times we have encountered the problem of the "fall" of the Internet which led to the abandonment of that course.

Despite all these limitations, the participants in the educational process get acquainted quite quickly with the virtual environment and with the way the information is transmitted to and from the teacher, and the results are positive.

3. How do I interact with students to see the level of understanding? How do I help them learn?

Regardless of the environment in which the teaching takes place, the student must be helped to understand the information transmitted. The teaching method must be transposed to the environment in which the teaching takes place. Knowing the multitude of temptations in the online environment and the fact that attention must always be captured in order to have positive feedback, the teaching strategy must be focused on the current needs of the student, who needs concrete at the expense of the abstract. Thus being always trained in the "teaching game", the student will be more receptive and will give the desired results. Task planning, organizing information, stimulating the interaction between student and teacher or between students by planning group tasks, all will contribute to a stabilization of the acquired notions.

4. How do I evaluate the student? (What evaluation methods do I use?)

We need to be aware that there are risks in the online environment, so testing methods need to be designed to be as difficult as possible. The most effective

assessment is the one that takes into account the evolution of the individual throughout the course by combining formative and summative assessment.

If until now the abstract of theory was palpable in practice, the student could get his hands on a machine, or could feel textures, smells that provided adjacent information about the product, now the concrete had to move to virtual, and physical machines were replaced with videos and process simulations.

None of this was possible without the help of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) tools, which expand the possibilities of the educational environment by using a wide range of software tools. These tools include modelling programs, search engines, electronic textbooks, focusing on the development of creative thinking. Students can engage in discussions that can take place on multiple online media, not just in the virtual classroom. They can meet online for joint projects and conferences on topics of common interest.

The penetration of technology in the field of education has initiated the development of new educational technologies, leading to a change in the teaching methodology of the technical, engineering component, forcing it to bring it to the current needs of the industry.

An engineering seminar using ICT tools is a software-methodological complex that offers the possibility to participate independently or with the involvement of a teacher to attend a training course for the masters.

The seminar discussed as an example is a clothing design seminar, successfully used during the pandemic lockdown.

To allow students to scroll through the content of the seminar in a logical sequence and for an easy search, the electronic module is provided with a content menu that allows quick scrolling to the desired information. The student needs the free installation of the software offered by Autocad and Gemini, the power point application and a youtube viewer.

To open the desired information, simply click on the link attached to the desired topic and the window will open for us to know. Navigating the page is simple, using navigation buttons or suggestive icons.

This teaching / learning method is based on viewing youtube videos and animations made with the help of various specialized CAD software, which illustrates the principles and notions learned and explained.

In addition, the student can repeatedly play, view clips and CAD applications in their own learning environment, until they are satisfied with what they have learned.

Even if it is more difficult and involves more extra work, this type of work contrasts with the formal teaching situation, in which the teacher controls the teaching method and there is no guarantee that students have managed to accumulate enough information in a short time.

Fig 4. Seminar navigation menu

Fig.5. How to make the pattern: classic

Fig.6. How to make the print taking into account the type of manikin

Fig.7. Fashion STUDIO is the flexible CAD solution for fashion industry

II. INVOLVEMENT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN A PANDEMIC CONTEXT

Also in a pandemic context, the question arises: is it enough to move the courses online? How do we replace sick teachers? Can we expand the range of technologies applicable in education? A complex and complicated subject, but one that opens up new horizons.

Artificial intelligence has had a significant impact in many industries, but can it also be applied in teaching? Can robot teachers be replaced?

It is well known that nowadays, technology has come to replace almost everything: electronic books are gaining ground in favor of printed ones, writing can be done on devices by "translating" language into writing, listening to a course can be done in electronic format, etc., but can technology replace the teacher?

The development of technology, especially artificial intelligence, has the advantage of bringing a development of educational technology, personalized to each student, so as to reflect the interests and learning capacity of each individual. Classic educational programs are boring for the new generation, but properly adapted Artificial Intelligence can make the learning process much more attractive.

New generations are more dynamic and need interactive learning systems, so classic teaching and assessment tools can create stress and unsatisfactory results. If AI systems are implemented, due to interactivity, students will experience a dynamic learning mode adapted to their needs, and the feedback obtained in real time will give the instructor the opportunity to modify problematic items.

Language learning chatbots are based on artificial intelligence and allow students to learn, communicate and know their performance with the help of robots.

Learning what they provide and quick feedback helps maintain optimal enthusiasm for learning.

But is this model of AI applicability also viable for engineering subjects? Can we apply this model to these areas as well? A large part yes! It can be created:

A content that is attractive and adapted to the intellectual needs of the learners. Chatbots can be created in which discussions can take place on topics of interest that vary from one day to the next.

Virtual laboratories can be created, where with the help of AI, the student can enter inside each component that is to be studied, to see if an action has a positive or negative impact following the VR simulation. This type

of laboratory not only provides information, but also provides a real response to the analyzes and simulations performed, creating real-time feedback on what the student has learned and what his weaknesses are.

With the help of already existing technologies: NLP, theFacts101, etc., the teacher can create attractive and captivating presentations and course materials, providing the information in a way that facilitates learning. AI helps to research the entire internet in minutes to bring out the most attractive and interesting topics on a given topic, which would take a human a lot of time.

Other systems that use artificial intelligence, such as Gradescope, help to quickly correct online tests but also to create sets of tasks and problems, exam questions. Thus, the creation and correction of various tasks is done quickly and the marking is done accurately, eliminating human error.

So, AI is helping to develop teaching techniques and methodologies, making it easier to design and create an effective curriculum that fits today's teaching requirements. Human replacement in the learning process I don't think can happen at any level! The teacher and his role beyond the didactic one cannot be replaced. New technology through all AI systems, robots or holograms, can provide assistance supporting the teacher in the teaching act to achieve maximum efficiency but cannot replace him from the learning process which is an art difficult to copy and quantified by programming logarithms.

A teacher is a guide, a mentor, a human inspiration that acts subliminally on the child's personality. How many of us came to love a subject or pursue profession x because of a teacher who believed in us or who at some point "charmed" us with oratory, knowledge, involvement?

Any programmable device can have time management or decision-making skills, but technology cannot replace human skills.

Over time, we will find that Artificial Intelligence becomes a valuable tool for trainers, but no matter how powerful it is, it cannot replace humans.

The COVID pandemic has shown the enormous value of personal education. Student interaction is much easier to facilitate in person and is generally very difficult to automate, making it a challenge for artificial intelligence.

As machine learning and artificial intelligence continue to advance, human interaction will become

even more important. Only teachers can truly understand the nuances of what goes on in the minds of their students in the classroom. Motivating students to practice and excel is a specific human skill that is difficult to program. Penalties or rewards provided by a device have no impact on students compared to the same action taken by a teacher.

However, artificial intelligence will continue to expand in this area as well, providing a beneficial learning experience for the development of future individuals.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the education of the future, regardless of the context: pandemic or not, will need the involvement of A.I. to create a strong education, adapted to current cognitive needs.

The children of the future are children who will work with PLCs and robots, and VR will be part of everyday life, so learning must be adapted to the needs of the future, by changing the teaching methodology and the means used.

Customizing engineering learning experiences with the help of AI by automating repetitive or time-consuming tasks helps to improve the performance of future engineers by providing real-time feedback and enabling the development of creativity but also the correction of informational deficiencies. Adjusting the program to the intellectual capacity of the information consuming student helps to actually improve results.

The only major obstacle is the economic one. Unfortunately, the high cost of AI tools is an obstacle for educational institutions but also for most students. The only more acceptable option is to use mobile AI technology. Through these applications, some of the handicap created by the still high cost of artificial intelligence technology can be reduced.

References

1. Ambrose, S. A., Bridges, M. W., DiPietro, M., Lovett, M. C., & Norman, M. K. (2010). *How learning works: Seven research-based principles for smart teaching*. John Wiley & Sons.
2. Biggs, J. B. (2011). *Teaching for quality learning at university: What the student does*. McGraw-hill education (UK).
3. Biggs, J.B. (1993), „From theory to practice: a cognitive systems approach”. *Higher Education Research and Development*, 12 (1): 73-85.

4. Blaga, M., Harlock, S. The eLiTa (e-Learning in Textiles & Apparel) Project. In: *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Virtual Learning ICVL, Iași (2009)*

5. Daggett, W. R. (2016), *Rigor and Relevance Framework*. International Center for Leadership in Education, Disponibil la: <http://leadered.com/our-philosophy/rigor-relevance-framework.php>

6. Herrington, J., Oliver, R., & Reeves, T. C. (2006). Authentic tasks online: A synergy among learner, task and technology. *Distance Education*, 27(2), 233–248.

7. Mayer, R. E. (2019). Thirty years of research on online learning. *Applied Cognitive Psychology*, 33(2), 152-159.

8. Nordmann, E., Horlin, C., Hutchison, J., Murray, J. A., Robson, L., Seery, M., & MacKay, J. (2020). 10 simple rules for supporting a temporary online pivot in higher education.

9. Opre, A., Miclea, M. & Iucu, R. (2011). *Calitate și performanță în activitatea didactică universitară*, Cluj-Napoca, Casa Cărții de Știință

10. Opre, D., (2013). *Fundamente psihopedagogice ale strategiilor centrate pe student. În Calitate și performanță în activitatea didactică universitară*, coord. Opre, A., Miclea, M. & Iucu, R., Cluj-Napoca, Editura Casa Cărții de Știință.

11. Peppas, A.P., *Distance learning in textile education*. În: *Proceedings of the International Conference AUTEX, Izmir, (2009)*

12. <https://cdn2.hubspot.net/hubfs/3409306/Best-Practices-in-Online-Faculty-Development.pdf>

13. <https://www.cnbc.com/2021/03/26/online-learning-boomed-during-the-pandemic-but-soon-students-return-to-school.html>

14. <https://bernardmarr.com/will-artificial-intelligence-replace-teachers/>

15. <https://www.agir.ro/buletine/1625.pdf>

16. <https://www.elearning.ro/promovarea-tic-in-educatie>

17. <https://ro.pinterest.com/pin/445786063104866162/>

18. <https://marketscale.com/industries/tag/algorithms-in-teaching/>